

Interactive, on-line software for Judd-Ofelt analysis – Introduction and demonstration

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ABSTRACT

The Judd-Ofelt (J-O) analysis, presented independently by B. R. Judd and G. S. Ofelt in 1962, represents one of the most important tools in the research and rare-earth (RE) doped optical materials and evaluation of their spectroscopic properties, including optical fibers. The J-O theory describes the $4f-4f$ transitions with three phenomenological J-O parameters, which can be in turn used to calculate transition probabilities, branching ratios and radiative lifetimes. This contribution presents a brief overview of the main principles behind the J-O analysis, and introduces a newly developed, interactive, online software for the unified calculation of J-O analysis of all RE ions, and demonstrates the functionality on selected materials.

Keywords: Spectroscopy, Rare-earth ions, Glass, Crystal, Judd-Ofelt theory, Silicate glass, Absorption

1. INTRODUCTION

Rare-earth elements and their trivalent ions remain highly relevant in both science and industry thanks to their unique magnetic, electronic and optical properties. The trivalent rare-earth ions exhibit sharp absorption and emission lines owing to the intra $4f-4f$ electron transitions, and rare-earth doped material are thus frequently researched and used for application in optics and photonics, e.g. in lasers or amplifiers^{1,2}. The Judd-Ofelt (J-O) theory, presented independently by B. R. Judd³ and G. S. Ofelt⁴ in 1962, represents one of the most important tools in the description of the $4f-4f$ transitions in various materials. The J-O theory three phenomenological J-O parameters, determined from measured absorption cross-sections, to describe the $4f-4f$ transition intensities, allowing to calculate transition probabilities, branching ratios and theoretical radiative lifetimes. Since the introduction more than 60 years, the J-O analysis has remained an invaluable tool for characterization and development of RE-doped materials, accounting for more than 6,000 entries in the Web of ScienceTM database. Due to the ubiquity of the J-O analysis, it is highly desirable to offer a comprehensive, intuitive and easily accessible on-line tool for its calculation. The newly developed Luminescence, Optics and Magneto-Optics Software (LOMS) provides an accessible, free-to-use tool for the JO analysis calculation, including combinatorial analysis, which allows to identify critical bands and transitions needed for a reliable and successful calculation^{5,6}.

2. SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

The J-O analysis provides a theoretical expression for the calculation of oscillator strength or line strength of a given $4f-4f$ transition, which includes the three J-O parameters as variables. The theoretical expression is equated with experimental values, calculated from measured transmission or absorption spectra, and the three J-O parameters are obtained by the least-squares method. The detailed equations are available in reviews by Walsh⁷ or Hehlen⁸.

The newly developed software LOMS provides an interactive tool for the comprehensive calculation and evaluation of the J-O analysis. The graphical interface of the software is depicted in Figure 1. The user selects the desired RE ions (all trivalent RE ions are available except Ce³⁺ and Yb³⁺), the type of input data (integrated absorption cross sections, oscillator strengths, line strengths), selects the used absorption transitions and provides the values of refractive index, or the

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